

Deliverable 2.5

‘A report on recommendations how EUTOPIA could identify and commercialise innovative research’

[Authors: Wendy Coy, Harriet Hine, Lewis Beer (University of Warwick)]

Corresponding author: H.Hine@warwick.ac.uk

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework programme under grant agreement No 101017419 EUTOPIA-TRAIN

Executive Summary

The EUTOPIA Alliance is a collaboration between ten universities in Belgium, France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, the UK, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Romania. One of the EU-funded projects under the EUTOPIA umbrella is called TRAIN (Transformation of Research and Innovation). Supported by the Horizon 2020 'Science with and for Society' initiative, the goal of TRAIN is to pool the resources and expertise of the six founding partners in order to develop a common Research and Innovation strategy for the alliance.

The outputs of EUTOPIA-TRAIN primarily fall into three categories:

- Mapping and evaluation reports
- New tools to facilitate collaboration
- New strategic documents or policy recommendations

This report seeks to identify the optimal ways in which EUTOPIA can identify and commercialise innovative research.

The report draws some key conclusions:

1. Commercialisation of research can result from research-led innovation, or from challenge-led innovation - i.e. the solution to a known commercial / societal problem, rather than a discovery.
2. Support for researchers and students in finding a path from discovery to commercialisation is helpful in aligning the pipeline to impact.
3. University-Business Collaboration that engages in a challenge-led approach to research and innovation has proved a successful methodology in some initial cases.
4. Identification of end users / markets in the design of research studies can provide a focus for research, innovation and commercialisation.
5. Awareness raising through education, networks, mentoring and support increase the culture of commercialisation and innovation.
6. Space, funding, equipment and programmes support a culture of innovation.
7. Recognition of innovation as a valid academic pathway enables time and verification of these activities.

The report will be used by the alliance to:

1. Identify and develop strategies and initiatives to identify and commercialise innovative research.
2. Share findings and best practice with each other and with other European University Alliances (EUAs).
3. Inform and support other areas of the TRAIN and MORE objectives and outputs.

Institutional Abbreviations

CY Cergy Paris Université	CYU
Göteborgs Universitet	GU
Univerza v Ljubljani	UL
Universitat Pompeu Fabra	UPF
University of Warwick	UoW
Vrije Universiteit Brussel	VUB

Table of Content

1. Introduction	5
1.1. Acknowledgements.....	5
1.2. Objectives of the deliverable	5
1.3. Definition of innovation.....	6
1.4. Pipeline approaches.....	6
2. Current strategies.....	10
2.1. Students	11
2.2. Researchers.....	12
2.3. External stakeholders.....	13
3. EUTOPIA initiatives	15
3.1. Mainstreaming entrepreneurialism	15
3.2. Practical measures for UBC.....	15
3.3. Database of external partners.....	15
3.4. GLENN office	16
3.5. EUTOPIA Business Developer Pool (EBDP).....	17
4. External stakeholder consultations.....	18
5. Conclusions	19
6. Recommendations.....	20
7. Appendix 1: EUTOPIA Network of Innovation leaders questions	21
8. Appendix 2: External stakeholder questionnaire.....	22

1. Introduction

The [EUTOPIA](#) Alliance is a collaboration between ten universities in Belgium, France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, the UK, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Romania. One of the EU-funded projects under the EUTOPIA umbrella is called TRAIN (Transformation of Research and Innovation). Supported by the Horizon 2020 ‘Science with and for Society’ initiative, the goal of TRAIN is to pool the resources and expertise of the six founding partners in order to develop our Research and Innovation activities.

This document constitutes the EUTOPIA-TRAIN deliverable 2.5, described in the TRAIN bid as a **report recommending how EUTOPIA and other networks of universities could develop and strengthen strategies to identify and commercialise innovative research.**

1.1. Acknowledgements

In addition to the authors credited on the title pages, we wish to acknowledge our other colleagues in TRAIN WP2: Simona Rataj (Univerza v Ljubljani), Camilla Pettersson (Göteborgs universitet), Tuur Roels (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Ana Sagardoy, Núria Brunet & Guillem Marti Cervera (Universitat Pompeu Fabra) and Pierre Viste (CY Cergy Paris Université). They have all contributed by engaging in discussions about the format and scope of the deliverable and giving feedback on the initial draft. We would also like to thank Sylvie Niessen (CY Cergy Paris Université) as lead for TRAIN WP4 (Human Capital). Our thanks are also extended to EUTOPIA’s new partners: Babeş-Bolyai University, Ca’Foscari University of Venice, Technische Universität Dresden and NOVA University Lisbon for their input in TRAIN-WP2.

1.2. Objectives of the deliverable

This deliverable is intended to help develop and strengthen strategies to identify and commercialise innovative research. As stated in the TRAIN bid:

Building on its work to expand the entrepreneurialism of researchers and students (WP2.2) and developing the effectiveness of the services supporting knowledge transfer at universities (WP2.3), this project will identify and test models designed to increase the scale of innovation at EUTOPIA alliance universities. This activity will be carried out in close collaboration with businesses and other end-users of research (p. 16).

The bid outlines the following steps to achieve these goals:

- Establish current strategies for identifying innovative research and building working partnerships with investors and others, identifying examples of good practice and barriers to progress.
- Consult external stakeholders (in conjunction with WP1.5) to obtain a better understanding of industry practice, advice on how to optimise opportunities to transfer knowledge, and support staff and student enterprise. This process will also allow external stakeholders to gain a deeper understanding of academic culture as well as the scale of opportunities for innovation available at

universities. This exercise will involve a minimum of six online workshops, face-to-face discussions, and blended formats.

- Jointly with external stakeholders, identify models that promote academia-business collaboration, engagement with businesses, not-for-profit organisations, venture capitalists and other actors in the innovation ecosystem (Link to WP3). Test these models jointly with the relevant external stakeholders and report publicly on the outcomes of the pilot studies.
- Develop a common policy for the EUTOPIA alliance.

Scope of the deliverable

Outputs of EUTOPIA-TRAIN have been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic which limited mobility opportunities and relationship building capacity, particularly with external stakeholders. Pilot initiatives have been explored and discussed with external partners through consultations. However, practical implementation, on an alliance level, has not been feasible at this stage of the project. Undertaking pilots with unfamiliar international partners was not workable on several levels. As identified in D2.4 (a database containing EUTOPIA external partners and researchers interested in engaging with them), trust plays a crucial role in relationship building and takes time to establish. On a practical level, differing organisational structures and local governance processes also make the implementation of pilots with external stakeholders challenging. Furthermore, funding for pilots with external partners was not included in the TRAIN budget. Ideas outlined in this report should therefore be explored and tested in EUTOPIA-MORE and future EUTOPIA projects. It is worth noting that most external partners consulted by TRAIN-WP2 already engage with universities on some level; further research should be carried out with businesses or industry which have not collaborated with higher education institutions. This would provide further valuable insights into barriers and enablers for university business collaboration. Finally, it is important to note that although new EUTOPIA partners have been consulted, the findings included in this deliverable and other TRAIN-WP2 deliverables are based on research carried out by the original six EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners (not the full ten partners of EUTOPIA-MORE), although the new partners have followed our progress through the Innovation Leadership group and EUTOPIA Week dissemination events.

1.3. Definition of innovation

EUTOPIA's definition of 'innovation' (as outlined in [Deliverable 2.2](#)) is the implementation of academic knowledge and knowledge-based assets and solutions outside of academia – not only technical products, but also other results of research, also from social sciences, humanities, and arts – and not only through commercialisation, but also through other pathways to impact, e.g. various forms of valorisation and collaboration with societal organisations.

1.4. Pipeline approaches

TRAIN-WP2 recognises that there are different ways to conceive the innovation pipeline for universities; approaches can be both **challenge-led** and based on **fundamental research**. Examples

of innovation pipelines include the University of Warwick’s 3-step model, GU’s innovation pipeline model, UL’s innovation pipeline model and the EU Commission’s Knowledge Square all illustrated below.

Figure 1. The inspire/educate/incubate model for the innovation pipeline at UoW

This diagram illustrates a 3-step model utilised by the University of Warwick to identify and commercialise innovative research through the key areas of **inspiration**, **education** and **incubation**.

AN IDEA'S JOURNEY FROM RESEARCH TOWARDS IMPACT IN SOCIETY, THROUGH OUR SUPPORT OFFERINGS

Figure 2. GU's innovation pipeline model, focused on the Innovation Office's processes

Figure 3. UL's innovation pipeline model

Links between EU GREEN Pillars

Figure 3. EU Commission Knowledge Square <https://eugreenalliance.eu/eu-green-pillars/>

The European Commission defines the Knowledge Square as a “concept understood as the junction of four core domains: **education, research, innovation and service to society** – Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on achieving the European Education Area by 2025” ([https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021XG0610\(02\)#NTR5-C_2021221EN.01001401-E0005](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021XG0610(02)#NTR5-C_2021221EN.01001401-E0005))

As an example of **challenge-led innovation**, the [West Midlands Health and Wellbeing Innovation Network](#) (WMHWIN) helps to address the real-world health-focused challenges through fostering and developing innovation. The WMHWIN seeks to encourage interested academics, students, businesses and SMEs to create the solutions, and supports their development through the provision of support, space, networks and mentoring. All with the aim of creating and commercialising innovative solutions for the benefit of the health and economy of the region and beyond.

2. Current strategies

This section of the report will outline current priorities and strategies identified across EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners to strengthen the innovation pipeline.

Innovation leads from across all ten EUTOPIA institutions provided input to seven questions with the aim of establishing common approaches to innovation (see Appendix 1). It was clear that the organisations prioritise innovation very highly as part of a third mission or strategy to develop the environment, society, lives of citizens and patients, while improving skills and the local economy. We are motivated by finding solutions for society's pressing challenges and being intellectually curious about our world. We would like to inspire the entrepreneurial and innovation passion with all players in our ecosystem, empowering multidisciplinary and cross communities to contribute to a fairer and stronger society capable of dealing with future challenges.

The EUTOPIA universities focus on the transfer of knowledge and talent in pursuance of societal, environmental and economic contributions, utilising a diverse set of innovation and entrepreneurial programmes that impact the region to focus on what is needed in the world next. We work in an open and inclusive manner to allow and encourage the best contributions from public and private partnerships, with a principle of being open to all, and inclusive so no one in our regions is left behind.

Members of the Eutopia Alliance provide and utilise platforms for innovation to identify, disclose, protect and commercialise research and ideas for impact in society, through our technology transfer functions. Our ecosystems develop and promote collaboration, projects and opportunities between researchers, businesses, investors and policy makers. We provide innovation spaces and programmes, advice and access to experts, with facilities for our stakeholders in order to put innovation into action.

We are passionate about supporting our local regions. Utilising and building on our existing assets (Science / Tech Parks, programmes, incubators and accelerators) we inspire our regional businesses, traditional industries, local authorities, and other academic partners to collaborate and build to bridge gaps in provision. We aspire to improve the regional economy through these partnerships by creating new companies, products, services and high-quality jobs. Whilst helping traditional businesses reinvent their business models, cost base and supply chain.

We support students, researchers, founders, and local people with education, incubators, accelerators, training, professional development, networks and events to help their development and find appropriate funding, support and partners.

Information included below has been drawn from the [Summary of Innovation-Related Provision](#), a working document, created at the start of the TRAIN project, which provides a more substantive and fulsome overview of the current structures and processes implemented by partner institutions to facilitate innovation. For the purposes of this deliverable, selected key initiatives are included below for reference and to provide context. It is also important to note that these strategies are constantly evolving and have changed over the course of the TRAIN project.

2.1. Students

All six EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners offer support to undergraduate and postgraduate students to raise awareness of entrepreneurship, provide entrepreneurial training and facilitate concrete entrepreneurial practice.

[CY Entreprendre](#) connects students with the surrounding entrepreneurial eco-system, both within the CY Cergy university (researchers, laboratories, [CY Foundation](#), and the [Design Hub](#) and associated [network of FabLabs](#)) and outside it (lawyers, accountants, communication agencies, business angels, and expert entrepreneurs). [Pépité France](#) is a network for student entrepreneurs, supported by the [Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation \(MESRI\)](#), and sponsored by the [National Research Agency \(ANR\)](#), which operates under the authority of MESRI.

At UPF, innovative educational initiatives are promoted and supported by the [Centre for Learning Innovation and Knowledge](#), or CLIK, and the [Educational Innovation Network](#) (incorporating the Units for the Support of Quality and Teaching Innovation, or USQUIDs).

[The Knowledge Transfer Office of the University of Ljubljana](#) and the Ljubljana University Incubator support innovative students with trainings, advice, mentoring and support when developing their business ideas. UL regularly organises start-up weekends, bringing together students with business ideas and companies, presenting their innovative challenges. UL also offers several interdisciplinary courses, where students solve real-life challenges. An example is <https://multidisciplinaren.si/>. UL supports students' innovative ideas through the [Rector's award for best innovation](#), targeting technological and social/humanistic/artistic innovation. Under the umbrella of the [Institute for Innovation and Development of University of Ljubljana](#) (IRI UL), the [Real Life Learning Lab](#) brings together interdisciplinary student teams and expert university and industry mentors to address current challenges. Within specific projects, students learn about project management, innovation processes, and entrepreneurial skills in a way that complements their degree studies, enhances their employability, and fosters the university's relationship with industry.

The University of Gothenburg produces a great deal of research on entrepreneurship and innovation, and provides research-led teaching on these subjects through master's and bachelor-level programmes in the [Unit for Innovation and Entrepreneurship](#) and the [Centre for Intellectual Property](#), both housed in the School of Business, Economics and Law. Students can also attend seminars at the research centre [U-GOT-KIES](#) (Gothenburg network for Knowledge-intensive Innovative Ecosystems). As well as enabling students to connect with leading researchers, there is also strong involvement from industry and public-sector professionals. Students often engage in simulated 'client projects' where they act as entrepreneurs/consultants under the guidance of academics and practitioners. Those 'clients' can be external companies and organisations, but also researchers in e.g. tech or life sciences from the university currently exploring their innovative idea supported by the [Grants and Innovation Office](#). The Grants and Innovation Office also supports student ideas that result from university-based activities such as education and research); other student ideas are supported primarily by partner organisations such as [Venture Cup](#) and [Drivhuset](#).

At the University of Warwick, cross-cutting all departments, [Warwick Enterprise](#) helps students and graduates of UW to develop entrepreneurial mind-set, skills and capabilities through a range of training activities and funding opportunities. Warwick Enterprise has strong relationships with academic departments and with student societies focused on entrepreneurship, including Enactus Warwick, Warwick Entrepreneurs, the LEAD Network (formerly Warwick Girl Boss), Warwick Incubator, Warwick Kickstart, Warwick SEED, Warwick TECH, and Warwick Women's Careers Society.

At VUB, the [For Future Entrepreneurs](#) webpage showcases how VUB aims to promote entrepreneurship among students through a variety of initiatives including (but not limited to) [Entrepreneurship seminars](#), [Guidance on starting a spin-off](#), and funding opportunities.

2.2. Researchers

EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners provide central support for researchers to engage with non-academic partners and to valorise and commercialise research through dedicated technology transfer/innovation offices.

[CY Transfer](#) maintains strong connections with the activities of researchers and uses a range of complementary tools (for detection, encouragement, support, management and transfer) to facilitate the commercialisation process. This work contributes to the competitiveness of local companies and thus helps to improve the attractiveness of the region. Doctoral fellowships in partnership with industry are facilitated through programmes such as [CIFRE](#) (Industrial Research Training Agreements), by the [Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation \(MESRI\)](#) and managed by ANRT (National Association of Research and Technology) and [CIREX](#), a framework created by CYU to develop regional and international partnerships and promote knowledge transfer. 8 CIREX programs have been financed, with €5m of private co-financing for €1.3m invested by the university.

The [UPF Innovation Unit – Business Shuttle](#) supports researchers from all scientific and technical areas. The Innovation Unit also runs a proof-of-concept support programme, [INNOvalora](#), co-financed by the government of Catalonia and ERDF funds. This is the first UPF programme to support translational and proof of concept projects linked to university research, and is intended to help researchers progress their ideas to the point where they can be evaluated by the private sector and, eventually, implemented in society. INNOvalora supports researchers with prototyping, market research, and IP strategy.

The [Knowledge Transfer Office of the University of Ljubljana](#) (KTO UL) acts as a bridge between the fields of research and business. KTO UL supports researchers and students with ideas and potential innovations, while also acting as an access point for companies on the lookout for technology, knowledge, or project partnerships. The [Innovation Fund](#), established in April 2020, is intended to help innovative projects reach a higher technology readiness level and engage with industrial partners and the market. The Rector's award for best innovation is also open to researchers – the winners receive a small financial reward and expert support from the KTO UL. Researchers regularly receive the “Izzivalnik” newsletter – an overview of industrial challenges from all over the globe. KTO UL also connects with international accelerators and incubators (in commercialising the research) and also participates in business ventures development, connecting researchers with entrepreneurs ([From Labs to Market](#), [Commercialisation Reactor](#)). UL also offers Makerlabs for students, developing their own ideas (by Faculty of electrical engineering, Faculty of mechanical engineering and Faculty of Computer sciences). The [Institute for Innovation and Development of University of Ljubljana](#) (IRI UL) identifies development needs of the economy and matches these with the expertise of UL researchers. It focuses especially on the: knowledge transfer to impact society, development and operation of research, support for IPR, disseminating research achievements, and R&I training and education.

The University of Gothenburg was one of the first in Sweden to create an integrated [Grants and Innovation Office](#). This office combines support structures for research funding, innovation and utilisation, IPR and legal issues, facilitating the transfer/valorisation process. It supports the verification/validation and development of a wide range of innovative ideas across the university, including those that may not lead to new businesses, but may develop existing businesses and other societal organisations through other routes of knowledge transfer/pathways to impact. [GU Ventures](#) started as a holding company intended to help the university connect with regional industries. Today it offers world-class incubation and funding for seed- and early-stage ventures, especially in life sciences and tech. As an incubator affiliated with the university, it has to turn a profit and therefore only works with commercially viable projects. This distinguishes it from the Grants and Innovation Office. VFT used to be applied only to commercial ideas but since 2018 includes a broader range of valorisation projects.

[Warwick Innovations](#) helps to identify, protect and transfer knowledge created in the University of Warwick out to businesses, where it can be developed into products and services that benefit society and generate economic benefit for partners, universities, staff and students. We have a small but specialist team which supports early-career researchers, doctoral students, and other members of the university, and they carry out a wide range of activities to achieve this commercialisation. Warwick Innovations also delivers [Midlands ICURe](#) on behalf of Innovate UK. This is a three-month programme open to teams led by early-career researchers from any UK university. It trains, funds and supports the teams to get out of the lab and validate their ideas in the marketplace. The [Deep Tech Innovation Centre](#) is an incubator/accelerator supporting students, staff, SMEs and alumni, currently working with its first cohort of businesses, with additional incubators / accelerators in Health and Wellbeing, Creative Futures, Clean Transport and a generalist stream. [University of Warwick Science Park](#) (UWSP) operates across four sites in Coventry, Warwickshire, and Solihull, hosting 120 businesses and supporting typically 300 businesses per year, from expanding start-ups to large companies.

[VUB TechTransfer](#) is the multidisciplinary operational team of the Vice-rectorate Innovation & Industry Relations. The team comprises 32 employees, organised into seven sections: business development, legal, EU support, philanthropic fundraising, industry-university networks, communications & events, and administration & management. Fundraising activities work in collaboration with [VUB Foundation](#) (which brought in almost €3m in 2019), and networking/communication activities with [VUB Crosstalks](#).

2.3. External stakeholders

EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners engage with regional businesses and organisations through a number of different routes.

At CY Cergy, spin-offs are developed with support from external partners such as [ERGANEO](#) (a member of the [SATT network](#) of Technology Transfer Acceleration Companies) and [BPI: Bpifrance](#) (see also their [English-language site](#)) which helps companies to think bigger and further ahead, offering financing solutions adapted to each stage of a company's life. The commercialisation of research is conducted at the regional level in collaboration with organisations that promote

economic development and scientific excellence. CY Transfer also enjoys strong links with the university's [alumni](#), who help to develop external partnerships and promote knowledge transfer.

At UPF, Bachelor's students have the opportunity to create an Integrated Final Project, known as the [inTFGrats](#), and this can be supported by the [Starting Lab](#) incubator. The aim is to nurture interdisciplinary creative projects between students in Communication, Economics & Business, Humanities, and the Polytechnic School, helping them to develop entrepreneurial skills and connect their work with the business world and Barcelona's cultural institutions.

Due to Slovenia's small geographical area, Slovenians have always been cooperating with other countries. The University of Ljubljana cooperates with national, foreign and international organisations (industrial partners, innovation support environment organisations, investors, other organisations). UL established the Ljubljana University incubator (supporting spin-offs and start-ups); UL is also co-founder of the Ljubljana Technology Park. UL is very much involved in the EIT KICs (Manufacturing, Health, Digital), in Strategic development and Innovation partnerships in Slovenia – SRIPs – connecting industry and research organisations on priority development and innovation topics (e.g. Factories of the future; Smart cities; Food; Advanced materials). UL is also cooperating with accelerators, incubators and deep-tech supporting platforms from all over the EU (AT, ITA, LT, SI) and is cooperating with the newly established regional POC fund (Slovenia-Croatia, supported by the EIF).

A key part of the University of Gothenburg's strategy involves [collaborating with external organisations](#) in order to have a positive influence on society and enhance the university's own research and education activity. Recent initiatives include a strategic partnership with the County Administrative Board of Västra Götaland (beginning 2019), including a specific collaboration with the School of Business, Economics and Law (within their [Partnership Programme](#)). However, most of the collaboration activities take place at departmental and faculty level, mainly through the many thematic and often challenge-based [centres of expertise and research](#).

The University of Warwick has long maintained good relationships with organisations in the Coventry & Warwickshire region, and in the Midlands more broadly. These include Coventry City Council, Warwick District Council, Warwickshire County Council, the West Midlands Combined Authority, the Coventry and Warwickshire Local Enterprise Partnership (CWLEP), the West Midlands Growth Company, University Hospitals Coventry and Warwickshire, South Warwickshire Foundation Trust and other NHS organisations, FE colleges, Schools and other universities in the region (e.g. by connecting with the University of Nottingham's [Ingenuity](#) programme), local business clusters such as the thriving video game industry in Leamington Spa, and initiatives such as [Coventry City of Culture 2021](#), among others. Warwick's Innovation Strategy aims to join the ecosystem members in the [Warwick Innovation District](#) to make more of the relationships with all groups – joining businesses and investors with academics and challenges to provide solutions.

Companies committed to supporting research and collaboration with VUB can find space, appropriate facilities or infrastructure in the research park or one of the incubation centres such as [Researchpark Zellik](#). The Flemish Government began to establish research parks in 1974 so that universities could work with regional development organisations to supervise research-oriented companies. The Researchpark Zellik in Brussels was established in 1983, with VUB assessing the research activities of companies who apply.

3. EUTOPIA initiatives

This section of the report includes EUTOPIA level strategies and initiatives to identify and commercialise innovative research. While some of these initiatives have been piloted by the alliance, others could be implemented in the future (subject to funding).

3.1. Mainstreaming entrepreneurialism

TRAIN-WP2's [Deliverable 2.2](#) seeks to identify ways to mainstream entrepreneurialism in the mindset of students and researchers on an alliance level. Pilots carried out by TRAIN-WP2, in conjunction with other WPs, indicate that training is an effective tool for developing a 'culture of innovation'. Targeted training for researchers at PhD and supervisor/mentor level has the potential to strengthen the innovation pipeline and increase university-business collaboration. Bespoke training for arts, social sciences and humanities can also unlock potentially innovative research beyond STEM disciplines. Rewards and incentives for engaging with innovative activity (through promotion and salary criteria) should to be explored at the alliance level to strengthen the innovation pipeline.

3.2. Practical measures for UBC

TRAIN-WP2's [Deliverable 2.3](#) aims to identify ways in which EUTOPIA partners can work together to improve connections with other actors in the innovation ecosystem across all European regions, in addition to the activities and support offered by our respective universities. Through consultations with external stakeholders including industry and business, WP2 recommends the following practical measures to strengthen university-business collaboration:

- Recognition of UBC in career development, mobility and scholarships.
- Further development of innovation support environment.
- Develop skill sets relating to university-business collaboration.
- Networking and communication to facilitate industry-academia collaboration.
- Develop supporting competences and engaging qualified facilitators.

3.3. Database of external partners

As part of [Deliverable 2.4](#), TRAIN-WP2 developed a prototype database of EUTOPIA's external partners and researchers interested in engaging with them. The database pilot, '[EUTOPIA TRAIN Deliverable 2.4 - database \(confidential\)](#)', is a confidential file that is only available to TRAIN WP2 members and European reviewers. The database constitutes a master-list of external organisations so far identified as a selection of existing partners by one or more of the six EUTOPIA universities, and therefore as potential partners for the other universities. This database fulfils the literal requirements of the deliverable but is not intended for wider publication. The report and its conclusions (summarised below) represent the more substantial part of the deliverable:

- **Demand:** There is an appetite for new collaborations, but little appetite for a database.

- **Relationships:** Finding new contacts is a challenge and a priority, but it is equally important to connect in the right way and manage relationships carefully once they have been initiated.
- **Tools:** There are existing tools that serve a similar function to the proposed database, which could be used instead or harnessed in new ways through a central resource.
- **Viability:** The database, if it were created, would need to exist in a form that could be populated with the necessary data and then kept up to date (and accessible) in the long run. We should remain open to the possibility that other EUTOPIA services may better support the enhancement of UBC.
- **Next steps:** We will work with our EUTOPIA colleagues to consider whether our prototype database should be developed further. We will also explore the potential of other tools and approaches that may help to identify and commercialise research.

3.4. GLENN office

EUTOPIA's [Grants, Legal and Innovation Office](#) (GLENN) has been set up as part of TRAIN-WP5. The GLENN Office purpose is to interconnect our universities' research and innovation support offices to allow offering better services to the researchers (end-users), contributing to the development of EUTOPIA common agenda and, ultimately, strengthening the alliance. Several initiatives set up as part of GLENN will help to strengthen EUTOPIA's innovation pipeline.

An 'Innovation working group' has been established under GLENN as an initial forum to share best practice and challenges between tech transfer staff and utilisation support. The aim of this group is to understand how GLENN can identify and support innovative research across EUTOPIA partners.

A 'legal working group' has also been established under GLENN to share best practice between university lawyers about legal support for research and innovation projects. This group will help the alliance to stay up to date with new legislation and explore how to make contracting processes as smooth as possible for new consortium agreements.

The GLENN Ordinary Response (OR) will be activated when there is a common interest in applying to an R&I funding call that is considered foreseen. A foreseen call is published by the funding entity following an ordinary procedure. It is expected to be announced and opened by the funding authority beforehand, and the potential applicants know about it long in advance. A clear example of a foreseen call would be those included in the biennial work programmes of the EU Framework Programme (e.g. MSCA-DN, ERC StG, Missions, etc.).

The Rapid Response (RR) will be activated under certain extraordinary circumstances, when EUTOPIA universities want to apply to an R&I funding call that is considered unforeseen. An unforeseen call is published by the funding entity at short notice, responding to an extraordinary situation. It is not expected to be opened by the funding authority beforehand, as it responds to a sudden change, and the potential applicants have very limited time to prepare until the call deadline. It does not include late reaction from researchers to foreseen calls. An example of an unforeseen call would be the extraordinary EU calls in response to the covid-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine.

3.5. EUTOPIA Business Developer Pool (EBDP)

The EUTOPIA Business Developer Pool (EBDP) was identified, in Deliverable 2.4, as an alternative tool to increase university business collaboration (UBC). The role of a ‘EUTOPIA Business Developer’ would be to establish connections with other business developers, connect researchers with other researchers within the EUTOPIA alliance and identify and develop activities supporting UBC such as networking events and small-scale mobility. The Business Developers would function as a single point of contact (SPOC) for each partner university and come together as a group to discuss further actions or improvements to build relationships with non-academic partners.

Figure 2: EUTOPIA Business Developer Pool

The EUTOPIA Business Developer Pool and other networks of professional staff (e.g. industry liaison officers and IP professional) might bridge the distance between researchers from the different EUTOPIA partners and at the same time create a centralised knowledge hub for strengthening the further EUTOPIA development on research and business cooperation. While it is not within the scope of the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project to change organisational structures within individual partners, this model could be piloted on an alliance level in the future as part of the GLENN Office outlined above.

4. External stakeholder consultations

An online [questionnaire](#) was designed by TRAIN-WP2 members and used to collect data from external stakeholders (see Appendix 1) to further understanding about the barriers and enablers for collaboration with universities. WP2 partners adopted different approaches to data gathering, producing a varied set of responses. Some partners conducted semi-structured interviews in person or online with external partners while others distributed the questionnaire more broadly, asking partners to complete the survey themselves. In total, 84 responses were recorded from a range of private, public and not-for-profit organisations. A thorough analysis of these consultations has been undertaken as part of [Deliverable 2.3](#) (A report on recommendations of how EUTOPIA could build engagement with innovation ecosystems), however some key findings are included here for the purposes of this report.

The implementation of pilots with external stakeholders has been challenging for reasons outlined in Section 1.2 under ‘scope of the deliverable’, however insights gathered through consultations can help to strengthen EUTOPIA’s innovation pipeline. Of the external stakeholders consulted, 87% currently engage with higher education institutions, and 47% of respondents cited ‘student placements/internships’ as the type of engagement with universities, followed by ‘contracts’, ‘thesis’ and ‘licenses’. Other types of engagement include (but are not limited to) ‘industrial PhDs’, ‘collaborative research & development projects’, ‘joint articles’ and ‘job fairs’. Stakeholders who do not currently engage reported ‘not enough time/resources’ as the main reason, followed by ‘not been approached’, ‘not been motivated’ and ‘not business priority’, however 72% of non-engaging stakeholders responded that they would be interested in working with universities in the future. Stakeholders who do currently engage indicated ‘personal contact’ as the way that the relationship was initiated, followed closely by ‘institutional relationship’. This mirrors key findings in [Deliverable 2.4](#) (a database containing EUTOPIA external partners and researchers interested in engaging with them) which indicate, from a researcher perspective, that personal contact, rather than a database tool, is a crucial component in cultivating collaboration with non-academic partners. External stakeholders consulted also identified other ways that relationships are built such as ‘mobility schemes’, ‘university alumni’ and ‘events’. Stakeholders ranked ‘networking events’ as the best way for universities to promote engagement with external stakeholders, followed by ‘open days’. A database of researchers and their expertise ranked lower but was still considered useful by some respondents. Survey results indicate that EUTOPIA-level networking events with business could have the capacity to strengthen the innovation pipeline moving forward.

5. Conclusions

The conclusions are drawn from work across WP2 and consideration of findings from other connected work packages in TRAIN and 2050, referred to in the main body of the report.

1. Commercialisation of research can result from research led innovation, or from challenge led innovation - i.e. the solution to a known commercial / societal problem, rather than a discovery.
2. University Business Collaboration that engages a challenge led approach to research and innovation has proved a successful methodology in some initial cases.
3. Support for researchers and students in finding a path from discovery to commercialisation is helpful in aligning the pipeline to impact.
4. Identification of end users / markets in the design of research studies can provide a focus for research, innovation and commercialisation.
5. Awareness raising through education, networks, mentoring and support increases the culture of commercialisation and innovation.
6. Space, funding, equipment and programmes support a culture of innovation.
7. Recognition of innovation as a valid academic pathway enables time and verification of these activities.
8. Formal programmes for incubation and acceleration form an important part of an innovation ecosystem.

6. Recommendations

The recommendations outlined below are based on research conducted by TRAIN-WP2 through a programme of stakeholder engagement activities over the course of the project. These recommendations feed into both EUTOPIA's Research Assessment Framework (WP3) and EUTOPIA's HR Strategy (WP4), particularly relating to reward and recognition, recruitment and training. While it is not within the scope of EUTOPIA to change institutional level policy, these recommendations could first be onboarded and piloted at an alliance level, or by some of the institutional partners, to strengthen the innovation pipeline through a top-down/bottom-up approach:

- Develop rewards and recognition for innovative activity on an alliance level (D2.2).
- Develop and design innovation training to increase potential for commercialisation and valorisation of research (D2.2).
- Develop central support structures to facilitate EUTOPIA's innovation pipeline (i.e. GLENN office).
- Recruitment of EUTOPIA business developers who are research area-based, semi entrepreneurs/promoters to help to identify and commercialise innovative research.
- Use existing tools to help identify opportunities to collaborate with external partners (D2.4).
- Plan and deliver networking opportunities/events for external stakeholders to meet researchers.
- Identify and secure investment for innovation and improve visibility towards the Vice Chancellors.
- Connect and exchange best practice with other European University Alliances (e.g. through European Entrepreneurship Hub).
- Use/leverage each other's resources (e.g. digital platforms such as [My Innovation Collective](#)).
- Strengthen the development of a focus on deep tech.

7. Appendix 1: EUTOPIA Network of Innovation leaders questions

Section 1: The principle that guides your culture, approach and focus for Innovation at your University

E.g. at Warwick we believe in an open and inclusive approach to innovation

Section 2: The assets, networks and foundations that allow your University to deliver innovation in a differentiated and compelling manner

E.g. at Warwick we believe these building blocks below give us a strong foundation

Section 3: How we work across our geography with other organisations to amplify our impact

E.g. at Warwick we have Innovation centres co-located with key sectors for the region and business districts

Section 4: Applying the principles in section 1, leveraging all the assets in our networks, across our geographic area these are the programmes which take place to help our communities prosper

E.g. at Warwick we have broad range of programmes designed to support academics in tech transfer, investors find great opportunities, students ideate and learn, and founders grow their businesses.

Section 5: Why do you believe in innovation so strongly

E.g. at Warwick we want to unleash the research, teaching and talent in our region to solve societal challenges and support the regions economy.

Section 6: How do you measure the traction of your innovation

E.g. at Warwick we look at awareness of our innovation, the volume of engagement in our programmes and the impact we make in terms of investment raised and businesses supported.

Section 7: Key priorities for the next horizon

E.g. at Warwick we are looking to grow commercial investment funds for our businesses, the scale of our impact across the region and the environment so that the best academics want to base themselves here to innovate.

8. Appendix 2: External stakeholder questionnaire

EUTOPIA-TRAIN

external stakeholder questionnaire

The EUTOPIA Alliance is a collaboration between ten universities in Belgium, France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, the UK, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Romania. One of the EU-funded projects under the EUTOPIA umbrella is called TRAIN (Transformation of Research and Innovation). Supported by the Horizon 2020 'Science With and for Society' initiative, the goal of TRAIN is to pool the resources and expertise of the six founding partners in order to develop our research and innovation activities our Research and Innovation activities.

The outputs of TRAIN will fall primarily into three categories:

- Mapping and evaluation reports
- New tools to facilitate collaboration
- New strategic documents or policy recommendations

Some exciting work has already been done during the first year of this three-year project, especially with regard to the first bullet-point above. We now have a large amount of data about our innovation-related activities, including a general overview and more detailed insights into support structures and training provision. We are now reaching out to external stakeholders from different sectors in order to understand, more fully, their level of engagement with Higher Education institutions and the motivators, barriers and solutions to University Business Collaboration (UBC). This is the purpose of the following survey. The questions in this survey draw on data, relating to the 6 founding EUTOPIA countries, collated in the State of University-Business Cooperation reports produced in 2017: <https://www.ub-cooperation.eu/index/reports>. These reports provide a pre-pandemic perspective and it is timely, in 2022, to revisit this subject through the lens of EUTOPIA.

The key goal here is to improve relations with external organisations in a way that increases and enhances knowledge transfer. A further long-term aim is to make the EUTOPIA partners, and their innovation eco-systems, more accessible to each other, so that good practices can be shared and new opportunities identified.

The questions we would like to ask you fall into the following categories:

- Current engagement with Higher Education institutions
- Relationship building
- Barriers and solutions to successful UBC

Section 1

1.Name

Enter your answer

2.Gender

Male

Female

Non-binary

Other

Prefer not to say

3.Organisation

Enter your answer

4.Sector

Private

Public

Not-for-profit

Other

5.If other, please specify below:

Enter your answer

Section 2

Current engagement

6.Do you currently engage with any Higher Education institutions?

Yes

No

Not yet but thinking about it

7.If yes, please specify which institutions:

Univerza v Ljubljani

University of Warwick

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

CY Cergy Paris Université

Göteborgs Universitet

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Other

8.If other, please indicate below:

Enter your answer

9.Please specify the research topics:

Enter your answer

10.Please specify the nature of engagement:

Contract

Thesis

Licences

Student placements/internships

Other

11.If other, please elaborate further:

Enter your answer

12.If you do not currently engage, please indicate why:

Not been approached

Not enough resource/time

Not been motivated

Not business priority

Other

13.If other, please elaborate further:

Enter your answer

14.If you do not currently engage please indicate in you would be interested in doing so in the future?

Yes

No

Maybe

15.If so, please indicate under what conditions:

Enter your answer

Section 3

Relationship building

16.Please indicate how the relationship was initiated:

Personal contact

Matching service

Institutional relationship

Recommended through other businesses

Web browsing

Other

17.If other, please elaborate below:

Enter your answer

18.What do you think would be the best way for universities to promote engagement with external stakeholders? Multiple choice.

Networking events

Open days

Adverts

Database of researchers and their expertise

List of laboratories and their expertise

Other

19. Please list other possibilities below:

Enter your answer

Section 4

Barriers and solutions to successful engagement

20. Among listed, what are the main motivators for UBC?

Get access to new technologies and knowledge

Improve the innovation capacity of our company

Positive impact on society

Access to new discoveries at an early stage

Obtain a customised solution for our business

Providing access to better qualified graduates

Obtain funding/financial resources from EU programmes

Improve the reputation of our business

Improve the skills of our current employees through training

Other

21. Please list any other motivators below (including personal):

Enter your answer

22. Have you experienced any of the following barriers to successful engagement with universities:

Licensing across borders

International competition rules

Rules on company ownership

Differing motivations between universities and our business

Lack of people with business knowledge within universities

Lack of government funding for UBC

Differing time horizons between universities and business

Bureaucracy related to UBC in universities and business

Universities' lack of awareness of opportunities arising from collaborating with our business

Lack of our own business funding for UBC

Lack of people with scientific knowledge within our business

The focus on producing scientific outcomes (e.g. papers by universities)

Other

23. Please elaborate further on these barriers:

Enter your answer

24. Please indicate how these issues were addressed/might be solved:

Enter your answer

25. In your experience, what are the main facilitators of UBC?

Existence of mutual trust

Existence of funding to undertake the cooperation

Existence of mutual commitment

Existence of a shared goal

Prior relation with the university partner

Flexibility of the university partner

Scientific orientation of our business

Interest of the university in accessing our knowledge

Other

26. Please elaborate further on these facilitators e.g. how do you establish trust etc.

Enter your answer

Section 5

Digital solutions

27. In your opinion, would tools like Industrial Challenges platform for EUTOPIA researchers (e.g. Innoget, In-Part, Halo Science) be helpful in boosting the cooperation between universities and your company?

Yes

No

Maybe

Don't know

28. In your opinion, would tools like Crowdfunding of research (e.g. Bicocca Universtita del Crowdfunding) be helpful in boosting the cooperation between universities and your company?

Yes

No

Maybe

Don't know

29. What other examples of tools and services (in addition to national and European financial instruments) do you see as helpful in boosting the cooperation between universities and your company?

Enter your answer

30. Have you explored any of the following digital solutions to innovation:

Virtual meeting platforms

Blended networking

Virtual mobility

Other

31. Please list other digital solutions that you have explored:

Enter your answer

32. If you have used digital solutions, please explain what you have found helpful:

Enter your answer

33. If not, please indicate why:

Availability

Effectiveness

Other

34.If other, please elaborate below:

Enter your answer

Section 6

UBC Focus Groups

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire. Once the results have been analysed we intend to hold follow-on focus groups/workshops around key emerging themes.

35.Please indicate whether you would be interested in participating in a follow-on focus group meeting or workshop:

Yes

No

36.If yes, please include your email address below:

Enter your answer